

The Anthropocene: proposal, rejection, consequences, alternatives and a lesson

Valentí Rull

Botanic Institute of Barcelona, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Barcelona, Spain. Email: vrull@csic.es

Abstract

The term “Anthropocene” was proposed in 2000 to denote a new epoch in the Geological Time Scale, characterized by the global human impact on the Earth system. In 2023, the Anthropocene Working Group submitted a formal proposal to the International Commission on Stratigraphy, which rejected it on the grounds that it did not meet the criteria for establishing a new geological epoch. Consequently, the Anthropocene currently lacks a formal definition or geological status. Because it was originally intended as a formal stratigraphic unit, its formalization must follow stratigraphic rules. The possibility of submitting a different proposal remains, but defining a globally synchronous chronological boundary—essential for a geological epoch—is challenging due to the heterogeneous and uneven nature of human impacts. Alternatively, the Anthropocene could be considered a geological event or episode, which are time-transgressive and do not require formalization, although this would necessitate terminological adjustments, since the suffix “-cene” inherently denotes an epoch in stratigraphic terminology. In the absence of a precise definition, the best approach is either to clarify the concept of the Anthropocene used in each case or to adopt a different name free of stratigraphic implications while a formal geological solution is pursued. Using the term to refer to anything other than a geological epoch is incorrect and may create inconsistencies. Currently, the Anthropocene remains in a definitional void but is widely used in environmental research, activism and broader professional and popular contexts. The genie is out of the bottle.

Keywords

Anthropocene, stratigraphy, terminology, geological time scale, epoch, event, episode, scientific accuracy

Introduction

The recent rejection of the Anthropocene as a new geological epoch by the International Commission on Stratigraphy (ICS), the responsible for defining the terms and units of the Geological Time Scale (GTS), has fostered amazement and disappointment across scientific, non-scientific and public sectors (Witze, 2024; Bourzac, 2025). This is particularly evident in contexts concerned with environmental issues, especially ongoing global change and its potential future consequences, where the ICS components may be perceived as part of a scientific elite disconnected from reality, or even as global change denialists (Voosen, 2016). A similar divide appears to exist between geological science and other disciplines—such as politics, economics, law, the arts and philosophy—where the term and concept of the Anthropocene have gained widespread use with a variety of meanings (Autin, 2016). In broader societal terms, public perception is highly influenced by the media, whose headlines and narratives do not help to bridge the gap between science and society (Hinde, 2026).

Although the Anthropocene and ongoing global change are conceptually closely related, they are in practice independent. The formalization—or not—of a new geological epoch will neither improve nor worsen global environmental problems, as these are primarily driven by socioeconomic rather than geological factors (Rull, 2013). Anthropogenic degradation of the Earth should be urgently addressed using well-established political, economic and sociological tools, and the formalization of a geological epoch such as the Anthropocene should not be invoked as a justification for action or inaction. In other words, global environmental problems are fundamentally rooted in human behavior, and responsibility should not be shifted to the presence or absence of a formal geological unit describing the situation.

This does not mean that the formalization of the Anthropocene is irrelevant, but rather that it should be addressed using stratigraphic criteria independent of previously established environmental considerations (Edwards, 2015; Finney & Edwards, 2015). These criteria are well established and are outlined in the International Stratigraphic Guide (ISG) (Salvador, 2013). As a scientific discipline, stratigraphy is evidence-based, and the definition of a new unit within the GTS should rely primarily on empirical evidence, including: (i) a stratotype, or the reference rock strata that define the new unit; (ii) stratigraphic markers, or the features that distinguish these strata from the underlying ones – in this case the Holocene; and (iii) a basal age, or the time at which the stratotype began to form. These features define the Global Boundary Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP), also known as the “golden spike,” for the corresponding unit – in this case, the “Anthropocene Epoch” – and should be globally recognizable and synchronous.

Terminological precision is also an important consideration. In the ICS International Chronostratigraphic Chart (ICC), which compiles the accepted time intervals of the GTS and their hierarchy, the suffix “-cene” is reserved for geological epochs of the Cenozoic Era (Paleocene, Eocene, Oligocene, Miocene, Pliocene, Pleistocene, Holocene) (Cohen et al., 2013). Therefore, the term “Anthropocene” corresponds, by definition, to a geological epoch. This has important implications, namely that the term cannot be used to refer to a geological era, a period or an age, and that it is terminologically unsuitable for defining a cultural or historical phase of humankind—practices that are not uncommon in non-geological literature and that generate considerable confusion.

It is important to recognize that scientific terms and concepts are governed by specific rules and definitions that must be respected to ensure accuracy. A common example is the definition of a new element in the Periodic Table, which must follow current standards and is supervised by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC). While anyone is free to use or not use scientific terms, those who choose to use them should adhere to the corresponding scientific standards. In other words, the use of scientific terms is unrestricted but requires consistency. In the specific case of the Anthropocene, those who choose to use this term should be aware that it refers to a geological epoch—or a prospective one—and nothing else. Using the term with a different meaning would require avoiding the suffix “-cene”.

The recent ICS decision regarding the Anthropocene was based on current ISG rules, without external influence from non-stratigraphic sectors. This commentary briefly summarizes the main features of this process, analyzes the consequences of its rejection a couple of years later, examines alternative proposals for characterizing human impact in geological terms and discusses potential future

developments. The context is stratigraphic because “Anthropocene” is, by construction, a stratigraphic term and was explicitly proposed as a candidate for a new geological epoch from the outset (Crutzen & Stoermer, 2000). However, the text, written by someone with a primarily ecological and paleoecological background, is fully accessible to readers without geological training.

The Anthropocene proposal

While the conceptual foundation of the Anthropocene—i.e., the planetary impact of human activities—seems clear enough, its translation into geological science remains elusive. The Italian geologist and priest Antonio Stoppani (1860) was the first to consider humans a geological force capable of producing global modifications detectable in the stratigraphic record. He regarded this as sufficient to justify the definition of an “Anthropozoic Era,” although he did not define it precisely due to limitations in the fossil record and the lack of adequate dating methods (Rull, 2020). This initiative remained largely ignored until nearly a century and a half later, when the Danish environmental chemist Paul Crutzen and the American ecologist Eugene Stoermer revived the idea and proposed a lower-rank geochronological unit, the “Anthropocene Epoch,” emphasizing anthropogenic changes since the Industrial Revolution and their stratigraphic imprint (Crutzen & Stoermer, 2000).

Therefore, both the original idea and the initial, more specific terminological and conceptual proposal of the Anthropocene, emerged within a geological context and were subsequently adopted by other disciplines, facilitated by the concept’s evident environmental significance. It is important to note that, although human activities and their consequences are intrinsic to the original concept, its geological nature lies in the requirement that anthropogenic impacts leave a clear imprint in the stratigraphic record. Otherwise, the proposal would rest on cultural or historical grounds, and the suffixes “-zoic” (typical of formal geological eras) or “-cene” (reserved for formal geological epochs) would not be part of the name. The use of these suffixes in terms such as “Anthropozoic” and “Anthropocene” constitutes an explicit statement of the geological character of these proposals.

Nearly a decade after Crutzen & Stoermer’s proposal, the ICS established the Anthropocene Working Group (AWG) in 2009, under its Subcommission on Quaternary Stratigraphy (SQS), to prepare a proposal on the Anthropocene as a new geological epoch succeeding the Holocene. In 2023, after 14 years of discussions, the AWG submitted its proposal to the SQS/ICS, considering that global human impact—and, therefore, the onset of the proposed “Anthropocene Epoch”—was evident in the geological record since the mid-20th century (Waters et al., 2024). In this proposal, the AWG suggested locating the stratotype in the sediments of Crawford Lake, Canada, and identified radionuclides—especially $^{239+240}\text{Pu}$ —released into the atmosphere by early atomic bomb tests in the 1950s as the principal stratigraphic markers (McCarthy et al., 2023). This boundary is globally recognizable across a range of sedimentary records, as demonstrated by auxiliary sections from the Baltic Sea, the United States, Japan, China, Australia, Antarctica, Italy, Poland and Austria. The proposed onset of the Anthropocene coincided with the Great Acceleration in population growth, industrialization and globalization, along with their associated planetary consequences (Steffen et al., 2015; Head et al., 2022).

The rejection

The AWG proposal was rejected by the SQS/ICS in 2024, and the decision was subsequently ratified by the International Union of Geological Sciences (IUGS). According to these bodies, the AWG proposal did not fulfil the stratigraphic requirements for the definition of a new geological epoch. They argued that global human impact began long before the 20th century in a time-transgressive, rather than synchronous, manner, and that a time interval of merely 70 years is inconsistent with the GTS framework, in which epochs typically extend over thousands to millions of years (IUGS, 2024). Proponents argue that an eventual Anthropocene epoch has the potential to endure for tens or hundreds of thousands of years (Summerhayes et al., 2024); however, this is a projection about the future and, as such, is not a geological target, as geology is concerned with the past (Finney & Edwards, 2015). Another important consideration is that the AWG proposal was not primarily evidence-based but environmentally constrained, and that it followed a reverse pathway to that required for the definition of a new stratigraphic unit, as outlined in

the ISG. Specifically, it first established a synchronous boundary—the Great Acceleration—then identified the stratigraphic markers that appear at this boundary, namely anthropogenic radionuclides, which reflect the onset of the atomic age rather than the beginning of global human impact, and finally sought the rock records that conform to these criteria (Waters et al., 2018).

The rejection was not difficult to anticipate, as both the results of the internal AWG discussions and the stratigraphic concerns raised by relevant ICS and IUGS members were frequently published in books and papers during the development of the proposal (e.g., Waters et al., 2014; Finney, 2014; Gibbard & Walker, 2014; Edwards, 2015; Finney & Edwards, 2015; Zalasiewicz et al., 2017, 2019). Immediately after the rejection, the AWG attempted to challenge the decision, citing irregularities in the internal SQS voting process (Witze, 2024; Bourzac, 2025), but the ICS/IUGS ratification closed the matter.

It should be clarified that the ICS and IUGS did not reject the concept of the Anthropocene in general, but specifically the AWG's proposal. A new definition remains possible; however, it would require submitting a new proposal to the ICS, likely by a newly formed working group, since the AWG was dissolved following the rejection of its proposal. Other proposed starting points for the Anthropocene—such as the Late Pleistocene megafaunal extinction (starting at ~50 thousand years before present or ka), the Early Holocene expansion of agriculture (~8 ka), the Old–New World contact (~1500 CE), or the Industrial Revolution (~1800 CE)—have been discussed in the literature (Lewis & Maslin, 2015); however, none of these proposals has been submitted to the ICS for formal evaluation. The possibility of submitting a modified AWG proposal has not been abandoned, and members of this working group continue to work on the topic outside the SQS (Summerhayes et al., 2024; Zalasiewicz et al., 2024; McCarthy et al., 2025). Therefore, the recent ICS/IUGS rejection can be considered neither the last word nor the definitive eradication of the Anthropocene, but only the dismissal of the proposal they received in 2023.

Unexpected consequences

The ICS/IUGS rejection led to an unexpected definitional void. Indeed, if the Anthropocene is neither a geological epoch nor a prospective one, as it was considered before the rejection, the term remains meaningless until an alternative definition is formalized, if one is ever proposed. Consequently, although the concept is clear in principle, from a stratigraphic perspective, the Anthropocene remains a term in search of a definition. Paradoxically, the only definition that remains invalid is the existing AWG proposal, which is also the only one that has been fully developed and officially submitted. At present, it could be said that the Anthropocene is anything but a geological epoch beginning in the mid-20th century and characterized by sedimentary anthropogenic radionuclides. Non-stratigraphic disciplines may exploit this conceptual clarity and the absence of a precise stratigraphic definition to adapt the concept to their particular interests. This practice existed even before the ICS decision, but the rejection has implicitly endorsed it. Therefore, the already existing decoupling of common usage from the formal geological status of the Anthropocene has been unexpectedly reinforced by the ICS/IUGS decision.

In addition, the ICS/IUGS explicitly validated the environmental use of the term in their rejection statement, which concludes by stating (IUGS, 2024):

“...the Anthropocene as a concept will continue to be widely used not only by Earth and environmental scientists, but also by social scientists, politicians and economists, as well as by the public at large. As such, it will remain an invaluable descriptor in human-environment interactions. But it will not be recognised as a formal geological term but will more usefully be employed informally in future discussions of the anthropogenic impacts on Earth’s climatic and environmental systems.”

This explicit acknowledgment of the meaning of the term beyond the stratigraphic domain seems contradictory to the formal rejection of the proposal and may encourage the decoupling of scientific and non-scientific interpretations. This stance could be seen as a gratuitous compromise to avoid criticism from environmental activists and scholars in the social sciences and humanities. Practically, this means that, as far as the IUGS is concerned, anyone may use the term at their own discretion – except to designate a geological epoch beginning in the 1950s. In this context, the Anthropocene can be defined as one wishes—or left undefined entirely.

Using the term “Anthropocene” without a precise definition is misleading because it implicitly assumes that it is a geological epoch, and therefore has a globally synchronous starting date and corresponding stratigraphic markers, even though these are not explicitly defined. As noted above, such an epoch could span a wide chronological range, from thousands of years ago to recent decades, making the lack of definition highly confusing. Nevertheless, this practice is not uncommon. It is also frequent to adopt the AWG definition despite its recent rejection. This approach was prevalent in many environmental studies before the rejection, but it is no longer tenable, as it lacks a stratigraphic basis. In the absence of a precise definition, the most objective approach is to specify the meaning of the Anthropocene in each case and to emphasize its provisional nature pending a definitive ICS resolution. Otherwise, the term will persist in the literature with an undefined meaning, subject to the particular criteria—or lack thereof—of each reader. As noted above, using the term in a non-stratigraphic context is not acceptable, despite the popularity of this practice.

Alternative proposals

The ICS/IUGS rejection document (IUGS, 2024) also suggested that the Anthropocene might be better regarded as an event rather than an epoch. This idea emerged a couple of years before the rejection of the AWG proposal and was led by prominent ICS members (Gibbard et al., 2022a, b; Walker et al., 2024). What distinguishes a geological event from a geological epoch is the time-transgressive and multitemporal nature of the former, which can range from seconds to millions of years and from local to global scales. A geological event is a transformative process that occurs gradually and unfolds at different times in different places. Consequently, it does not require a globally synchronous starting date and thus does not need a formalization protocol.

A well-known example of a geological event is the Great Oxidation Event (GOE) of the Proterozoic, which occurred between ca. 2.5 and 2.0 billion years ago (Ga) and fundamentally altered life on Earth by creating an aerobic atmosphere that enabled terrestrial life. The GOE represents a process rather than a chronostratigraphic unit of the GTS and, as such, is not represented by any specific GSSP. The Cambrian Explosion (CE; ca. 540–530 million years ago, Ma) and the Great Ordovician Biodiversification Event (GOBE; ca. 485–460 Ma) are other examples of geological events that lack global synchrony yet had a worldwide impact.

The Anthropocene Event (AE) may therefore be a more appropriate concept to describe the process of Earth’s anthropization, which began at different times depending on the region considered but ultimately came to affect the entire planet (Gibbard et al., 2022a, b). The AE was defined as the progressive transformation of Earth by humans since the Late Pleistocene (~50 ka). This term and concept, however, contain a terminological inconsistency—namely, the use of the suffix “-cene”, which is incorrect for units other than geological epochs (Head et al., 2023). AWG members disagreed with the event concept and instead proposed the Anthropogenic Modification Episode (AME), which is free from terminological issues (Waters et al., 2022). These authors emphasized that, whereas geological events are discrete and relatively short-lived occurrences—such as a volcanic eruption or a meteorite impact—geological episodes refer to prolonged processes, or series of related events, such as mountain building or widespread volcanism. Therefore, the GOE, the CE and the GOBE would be considered episodes rather than events.

The AME was defined as an informal unit encompassing the time interval during which humans have been modifying the Earth, with a duration of at least 50 ka (Late Pleistocene onward). Within this framework, the Great Acceleration is regarded as a set of synchronous events—collectively referred to as the Great Acceleration Event Array (GAEA)—which marks the beginning of the Anthropocene, as defined by the AWG and later rejected by the ICS. However, this view was not shared by the proponents of the AE, who maintained the need to disentangle the Anthropocene from the assumption that it must represent a specific time interval (Edgeworth et al., 2024). Recently, the term Global Humanization Event/Episode (GHE) was proposed, which also avoids terminological problems and aligns with previously defined geological events/episodes (GOE, CE, GOBE) (Rull, 2025).

Summary and final remarks

As a stratigraphic term and concept subject to scientific scrutiny, the definition of the Anthropocene should follow the criteria established by the ICS, just as the inclusion of a new element in the Periodic Table follows IUPAC rules. If the ICS considers the AWG proposal unsuitable, a formal definition remains pending until a new proposal is submitted and approved; in the meantime, the Anthropocene lacks a formal definition.

If, for some reason, a definition is required—for example, in a dictionary or encyclopedia addressing the topic due to its increasingly widespread use—one option consistent with current scientific standards could be: “A proposal for a new geological epoch following the Holocene—beginning in the mid-20th century and characterized by the irreversible global human impact on the Earth system—which was submitted to and rejected by the scientific bodies responsible for defining the units of the Geological Time Scale.” A less specific option, not focused on the AWG proposal, could be: “A proposal for a new geological epoch following the Holocene—characterized by the irreversible global human impact on the Earth system—lacking precise chronological and stratigraphic definition.” Both versions reflect the current status of the term, although the second implicitly leaves room for future proposals.

Ideally, these definitions could be complemented by considering the concept as an event/episode rather than an epoch. In that case, according to current stratigraphic rules, the suffix “-cene” should be avoided, and an alternative term such as Global Humanization Event/Episode (GHE) could be used. Disciplines other than geology may also adopt these definitions or wait for an eventual stratigraphic pronouncement. However, if they prefer to develop their own terms and concepts independently of current geological standards, they should define them accordingly and avoid the suffix “-cene”. What is inconsistent is the use of a scientific term such as “Anthropocene” with a meaning different from that of a geological epoch. Of course, as stated by the British geologist Philip Gibbard, an ICS member: “The ICS is not a police force and cannot stop people using terms” (pers. comm.). Therefore, the points raised here should not be considered legal or moral statements, but rather calls for consistency with established stratigraphic standards aimed at facilitating transdisciplinary communication and enhancing public awareness.

A take-home message for environmentalists could be: let stratigraphers handle terminological and conceptual matters—they know what they are doing—while continuing to work actively to prevent or mitigate Earth’s overexploitation, contamination and waste accumulation for the benefit of humankind. Similar messages could be directed to other scientific and non-scientific disciplines, including journalism. A general message to all of them could be: support interdisciplinary engagement and communication by using a standardized and recognized language, preferably based on scientific standards.

The lesson

If you decide to play the geological game, you should follow the geological rules. Stratigraphic rigor is not required if you opt for non-stratigraphic terms and concepts. Had Crutzen & Stoermer (2000) proposed that we have entered a new historical or cultural phase of humankind using a term devoid of specific stratigraphic burden, the outcome would have been different. However, they chose to propose a new geological epoch characterized by a formal stratigraphic term: the “Anthropocene.” Therefore, the reasonable response was for the geological bodies governing the GTS to create a working group to elaborate a detailed proposal to be submitted for approval or rejection, according to current ISG rules. Further progress and the corresponding outcomes have been detailed above. Now we still have the option of reformulating the proposal or leaving the geological arena to use a different term. The problem is that the term “Anthropocene” has gained immense popularity outside geology and appears to be here to stay (Ruddiman et al., 2015), regardless of its accuracy and meaning. The genie is out of the bottle.

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